

Uncertainty in Real-World Vehicle Routing: Appendix

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Abstract. This text is the appendix of the paper *Uncertainty in Real-World Vehicle Routing* presented at the *European Conference on Artificial Intelligence 2024* in Santiago de Compostela, Spain.

1 Appendix A: Formal model of the real-world problem

The real-world problem is a variant of the pickup-delivery problem including a number of additional features and constraints. We first introduce the graph behind the model and the relevant notation and then formulate the integer programming model of the problem.

Table 1. Notation related to the problem graph.

Notation	Description
G	graph with nodes V and edges E
V	set of nodes in G
E	set of edges in G
P	set of pickup nodes
D	set of delivery nodes
\mathcal{T}	set of start depot nodes
\mathcal{T}'	set of end depot nodes
τ_k	start depot node of vehicle k
τ'_k	end depot node of vehicle k
d_{ij}	distance-cost of edge $(i, j) \in E$
t_{ij}	time-cost of edge $(i, j) \in E$
n	number of customer requests
m	number of vehicles

1.1 Graph

The notation related to the problem graph $G = (V, E)$ is in Table 1. There are four types of nodes in G . The set P are nodes representing pickup locations of customer requests, and the set D are nodes representing the delivery locations of customer requests. $\mathcal{T} = \{\tau_1, \dots, \tau_m\}$ and $\mathcal{T}' = \{\tau'_1, \dots, \tau'_m\}$ are the start and end depot nodes of vehicles, respectively. The number of vehicles is m . Note that the start and end depot of one vehicle are in the same physical location, but each has its own node in the model. Thus, the set of nodes is defined as $V = P \cup D \cup \mathcal{T} \cup \mathcal{T}'$. We note that with n being the number of customer requests, $|P| = |D| = n$, i.e., pickup and delivery of each customer request has its own node in the graph regardless of potentially shared physical locations. If nodes in V are indexed, nodes 1 to n are nodes from P , nodes $n + 1$ to $2n$ are from D , nodes $2n + 1$ to $2n + m$ are from \mathcal{T} , and nodes $2n + m + 1$ to $2n + 2m$ are from \mathcal{T}' . Importantly, the delivery node in pair with the

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Table 2. Notation used throughout the model.

Notation	Description
K	set of vehicles
S_k	set of requests compatible with vehicle $k \in K$
i, j	indices used for graph nodes from V
k	index used for vehicles from K
T_k^{\max}	duration limit of vehicle $k \in K$
D_k^{\max}	traveled distance limit of vehicle $k \in K$
C_k^{pallets}	pallet capacity of vehicle $k \in K$
C_k^{weight}	weight capacity of vehicle $k \in K$
est_i	start of the time window at node $i \in V$
lst_i	end of the time window at node $i \in V$
s_i	service time at node $i \in V$
q_i^{pallets}	pallets quantity associated with node $i \in V$
q_i^{weight}	weight quantity associated with node $i \in V$
x_{ijk}	binary variable denoting whether the edge $(i, j) \in E$ is traversed by vehicle $k \in K$
A_{ik}	variable denoting the arrival time of vehicle $k \in K$ to node $i \in V$
Q_{ik}^{pallets}	variable tracking the number of pallets on vehicle $k \in K$ on arrival to node $i \in V$
Q_{ik}^{weight}	variable tracking the load weight on vehicle $k \in K$ on arrival to node $i \in V$

pickup node i has the index $i + n$ (both pickup and delivery nodes are sorted identically). The set of edges is defined as follows:

$$E = (V \times V) \setminus ((V \times \mathcal{T}) \cup (\mathcal{T}' \times V))$$

This matches the full cartesian product of the node set without incoming edges into the start depots and outgoing edges from the end depots.

1.2 Formal model

The notation used throughout the model is summarized in Table 2. We start by introducing the decision variables and their domains.

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_{ijk} &\in \{0, 1\} & \forall (i, j) \in E & \quad \forall k \in K \\
 A_{ik} &\geq 0 & \forall i \in V & \quad \forall k \in K \\
 C_k^{\text{pallets}} &\geq Q_{ik}^{\text{pallets}} \geq 0 & \forall i \in V & \quad \forall k \in K \\
 C_k^{\text{weight}} &\geq Q_{ik}^{\text{weight}} \geq 0 & \forall i \in V & \quad \forall k \in K
 \end{aligned}$$

The binary variables x_{ijk} track whether the vehicle $k \in K$ traverses the edge $(i, j) \in E$ in the solution. The variables A_{ik} are used to track the arrival time of the vehicle $k \in K$ to the node $i \in V$. Note that the variables are, in principle, redundant for nodes not visited

by the given vehicle. Variables Q_{ik}^{pallets} and Q_{ik}^{weight} track the load in terms of pallets and weight in the vehicle $k \in K$ on arrival to node $i \in V$. The same note on redundancy holds. With these variables, the model is given by the constraints and objective presented below.

Equations 1 and 2 ensure that each vehicle leaves its start depot and arrives to its end depot.

$$\sum_{j \in P \cup \{\tau'_k\}} x_{\tau_k, j, k} = 1 \quad \forall k \in K \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{i \in D \cup \{\tau_k\}} x_{i, \tau'_k, k} = 1 \quad \forall k \in K \quad (2)$$

Equation 3 ensures that if a vehicle enters a pickup or delivery node, it also leaves it.

$$\sum_{i \in P \cup D \cup \{\tau_k\}} x_{ijk} - \sum_{i \in P \cup D \cup \{\tau'_k\}} x_{jik} = 0 \quad \forall k \in K \quad \forall j \in P \cup D \quad (3)$$

Equation 4 checks that each pickup or delivery node is visited by exactly one vehicle exactly once.

$$\sum_{k \in K} \sum_{i \in P \cup D \cup \{\tau_k\}} x_{ijk} = 1 \quad \forall j \in P \cup D \quad (4)$$

At this point, the Equations 1 to 4 together ensure that a path from τ_k to τ'_k exists for all $k \in K$. Note that cycles detached from this path may still occur, these are resolved by introducing the time aspect. After ensuring basic route properties, we introduce tracking of time for each route.

Equation 5 introduces time-precedence on arrivals A_{ik} based on the traversed edges. The constraint creates precedence on arrivals for each traversed edge x_{ijk} by accounting for travel times t_{ij} and service times s_i . Note the applied max function, describing the possibility of waiting if the vehicle arrives before the time window at the location opens. Due to the $\text{sgn}(d_{ij})$ term, the service time is incurred only if we travel a non-zero distance. This allows for the described aggregation of service times across multiple actions within one stop at a physical location¹.

$$x_{ijk} = 1 \implies \max(A_{ik}, \text{est}_i) + s_i \cdot \text{sgn}(d_{ij}) + t_{ij} = A_{jk} \quad \forall k \in K \quad \forall (i, j) \in E \quad (5)$$

The established time-tracking now allows us to properly handle the pickup-delivery characteristic in our problem. First, Equation 6 ensures that both the pickup and delivery nodes of one customer request are served by the same vehicle.

$$\sum_{i \in P \cup D \cup \{\tau_k\}} x_{ijk} - \sum_{i \in P \cup D \cup \{\tau_k\}} x_{i, j+n, k} = 0 \quad \forall k \in K \quad \forall j \in P \quad (6)$$

Second, we need to ensure that the visit to the pickup node precedes the visit to the delivery node within the route as in Equation 7. We express the precedence based on the introduced time tracking.

$$A_{ik} \leq A_{i+n, k} \quad \forall k \in K \quad \forall i \in P \quad (7)$$

¹ For a sequence of actions in the same physical location, the aggregation described in Equation 5 counts only the service time of the last action. We note that we take the maximum of such service times in our implementation, this simplification was done not to overcomplicate the model.

At this point, the constraints so far ensured that proper routes are formed, each location is visited exactly once, cycles may not occur², and the pickup-delivery characteristic is in place. We proceed by defining the remaining constraints.

Equations 8 and 9 introduce load tracking for pallet space and weights, respectively. We note that the quantities q_i^{pallets} and q_i^{weight} are positive numbers at the pickup nodes, negative numbers at the delivery nodes (matching their paired pickups) and zero elsewhere.

$$x_{ijk} = 1 \implies Q_{jk}^{\text{pallets}} = Q_{ik}^{\text{pallets}} + q_i^{\text{pallets}} \quad \forall k \in K \quad \forall (i, j) \in E \quad (8)$$

$$x_{ijk} = 1 \implies Q_{jk}^{\text{weight}} = Q_{ik}^{\text{weight}} + q_i^{\text{weight}} \quad \forall k \in K \quad \forall (i, j) \in E \quad (9)$$

The tracking variables are then used in Equations 10 and 11 to introduce the respective capacity constraints.

$$Q_{ik}^{\text{pallets}} \leq C_k^{\text{pallets}} \quad \forall k \in K \quad \forall i \in V \quad (10)$$

$$Q_{ik}^{\text{weight}} \leq C_k^{\text{weight}} \quad \forall k \in K \quad \forall i \in V \quad (11)$$

Equation 12 introduces the time window constraints. Note that this also covers the time windows in which the vehicles must start their service. The value $A_{\tau_k k}$ is then interpreted as the start of service of the vehicle $k \in K$.

$$A_{ik} \leq \text{lst}_i \quad \forall k \in K \quad \forall i \in V \quad (12)$$

Equation 13 limits the duration of each route.

$$A_{\tau'_k, k} - A_{\tau_k, k} \leq T_k^{\text{max}} \quad \forall k \in K \quad (13)$$

Equation 14 limits the traveled distance in each route.

$$\sum_{(i, j) \in E} x_{ijk} d_{ij} \leq D_k^{\text{max}} \quad \forall k \in K \quad (14)$$

Equation 15 constrains the compatibility of customer requests and vehicles. Requests may be incompatible with vehicles, e.g., due to the height of the load or special vehicle equipment needed to serve the request.

$$\sum_{i \in P \cup D \cup \{\tau_k\}} x_{ijk} = 1 \implies j \in S_k \quad \forall k \in K \quad \forall j \in P \quad (15)$$

Lastly, the Equation 16 specifies the objective, i.e., the minimization of the total traveled distance.

$$\text{minimize} \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{(i, j) \in E} x_{ijk} d_{ij} \quad (16)$$

We note that this model describes the static deterministic version of our real-world problem not accounting for any uncertainties. Uncertainties may be introduced into the model exactly as we propose in the main text, i.e., by understanding the key quantities as random variables instead of constants and reinterpreting the meaning of the model accordingly.

² The formulation potentially allows zero-time cycles. These can be prevented by disallowing reflective edges and ensuring that all t_{ij} are set to at least ε .

2 Appendix B: Capacity penalties implementation for pickup-delivery problem

The main text of the paper describes the penalty and chance constraint strategies for canonical *capacitated vehicle routing problem* (CVRP). Here, we describe how these strategies are efficiently implemented into our *adaptive large neighborhood search* (ALNS) solver for complex real-world *pickup-delivery problems* (PDP).

The major difference from canonical CVRP is that the utilization of vehicles changes through the route in PDP as the vehicle loads and unloads freight. Consequently, the utilization of a vehicle cannot be expressed as a single number per route as in CVRP. Our implementation addresses this by penalizing or constraining each *stop* in the route separately. In our modeling, each route consists of stops, and each stop includes one or more *actions*. Actions are either pickup or delivery of a specific customer request. This modeling allows us to grasp the concept of a vehicle unloading multiple request loads in the same warehouse within one atomic step. Each stop, as an aggregate of actions sharing the same location, is associated with its departure load, i.e., the utilization of the vehicle upon finishing all the actions at the given stop. In analogy, we may calculate the expected total load and variance of total load upon departure from a stop.

For each stop, we calculate a penalty or check chance constraint as described in the main text based on the expected total load and variance of total load upon departure. The penalty for a route is given as a sum of its stop penalties. A stop penalty is not counted if the stop involves solely delivery actions as such a stop may not result in capacity failure. The total penalty is again given as a sum of route penalties weighted in the objective.

Regarding efficiency, the route penalties and chance constraints may be easily recalculated in $\mathcal{O}(n)$ since the expected values and variances of the total load are additive quantities under the assumption of load independence. In our solver, we recalculate these quantities and stop penalties (together with other information) after each change to the route (insertion or removal of a request). Incremental evaluations are applied when finding the cheapest request insertion, removals do not use the risks in their logic. The incremental evaluations are performed in $\mathcal{O}(1)$, i.e., the asymptotical complexity is not increased by introducing the penalty or chance constraints.

Finding the cheapest insertion for a pickup-delivery request into a route proceeds as follows. We systematically explore all pairs of pickup-delivery indices within the route. The pickup indices are iterated over in the outer loop, delivery indices in the inner loop, both are explored in an ascending order. In asymptotical terms, this procedure requires $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ steps w.r.t. the number of stops in the route.

At the start of each iteration of the outer loop (new pickup index), we recalculate the expected value and variance of the load upon departure from the newly inserted pickup stop. This is done based on the precalculated information about the previous stop allowing for $\mathcal{O}(1)$ complexity. These two statistics allow for incrementally recalculating the penalty or checking the chance constraint for the newly inserted pickup stop. Then, we calculate one step forward toward the delivery stop being inserted. The rest of the route (before inserted pickup and after inserted delivery stops) remains unchanged in terms of capacity penalties or chance constraint validity.

In the next iteration of the inner loop (next delivery index), we reuse the information from the previous delivery index. Information about the pre-delivery stop from the previous delivery index (this is the inserted pickup stop in case of the second delivery index) allows us to make one $\mathcal{O}(1)$ step to obtain information about the current pre-delivery stop. This dynamic programming approach allows

us to calculate penalties and verify chance constraint validity step-by-step incrementally with $\mathcal{O}(1)$ complexity for each pair of pickup and delivery indices. Consequently, the newly introduced penalties or chance constraints do not increase the overall asymptotical complexity.

3 Appendix C: Choice of parameter values

As demonstrated in the experimental analysis, the cost-risk trade-off can be smoothly steered by the relevant parameters in all the introduced methods. However, the natural question is how to choose the specific parameter values appropriately. Although the appropriate choice inherently depends on the specific application, we stress two problem-specific properties that play a vital role in this task and provide several rules of thumb that help to translate identified requirements to specific parameter values.

The primary factor affecting proper parameterization is the application-specific failure costs. Depending on the application, the consequences of failures range from inconveniences like postponing the given service to the next day to financial losses arising from contract-based financial compensations or even lost customers. In specific applications such as disaster relief planning, the failures may even result in the inability to save lives and substantial material values. Overall, the appropriate risk aversion directly translating to the choice of parameters should strongly reflect the general severity of failure-related consequences for the given context.

Second, in usual VRP applications for logistics, such as our problem, the daily operations involve human experts using software tools such as VRP solvers to assist them in making decisions. With practical operations requiring human experts in the loop, the choice of parameters must naturally reflect their preferences and needs. In other words, if the tool aims to assist an expert, well-set parameters directly relate to their user experience. Such a user preference elicitation process should ideally involve a continuous feedback loop allowing for further preference modeling.

3.1 Rules of thumb

The two aforementioned aspects are the key to identifying the required degree of risk aversion. Next, we provide several observations from the experiments with homogeneous uncertainties to help better map such requirements to reasonable ranges of the parameters.

For the inflation strategy and both capacities and times, inflation factors below 0.5 generally provide insufficient protection against failures. Values between 0.5 to 1.0 provide a smooth transition from risky to conservative solutions. Values above 1.5 generally eliminate a vast majority of the involved risks. Beyond this point, further risk reduction comes at a very high cost in traveled distance. If very conservative solutions are of interest, knowledge of the worst cases for the uncertain values is important in order not to overinflate any particular resource demand. The extreme case using only the worst-case values, in fact, matches classical worst-case robust optimization.

Similar observations hold regarding the chance constraint strategy, but the described parameter ranges are generally shifted. Since the inflation strategy overcompensates risks compared to chance constraints, the same value of inflation factor and shift for chance constraints result in milder risk aversion in chance constraints.

For the deflation strategy and capacities, we observed that deflating the vehicle capacity by $X\%$ on problems with $X\%$ of homogeneous uncertainty generally yields solutions with low fail rates (below 5%). For deflation strategy and times, we would recommend the

inflation strategy as a better alternative due to comparable simplicity and arguably better performance as per the experiment results.

For the penalty strategy and both capacities and times, we do not recommend using zero or very low values of the shift parameter. This setting generally provides little systematic control over uncertainties providing solutions with highly variable fail rates. Shift values from 0.5 to 1.0 provide a similar transition region as for the inflation strategy. Higher values are, again, rather overly conservative. In principle, the shift parameter sets a hard chance constraint. The weight parameter then allows for fine-tuning the risk aversion primarily driven by the shift parameter. Second, the weight parameter should also reflect the units of the primary objective. The weight values from the experiments were used together with distances measured in kilometers. However, if meters were used instead, we would need to use 1,000 times larger weight to achieve exactly the same tradeoff effects.

Lastly, to achieve comparable risk aversion, instances with heterogeneous uncertainties generally require stricter parameterization than homogeneous ones. The presence of highly uncertain inputs (even in smaller numbers) results in heavier tails of the tradeoff curves. This directly matches the intuition that eradicating risks arising from large uncertainties typically comes at a high cost.

4 Appendix D: Scaling experiment – runtimes

Tables 3 and 4 contain average runtimes (in seconds) of the 25,000 iteration runs for groups given by instance and uncertainty-handling strategy. The values in groups are averaged across repeated runs and parameterizations as they turned out to play no systematic role. We note that the runtimes were obtained using our adaptive large neighborhood search (ALNS) solver for complex real-world pickup-delivery problems. The runtimes are thus naturally higher than those of dedicated state-of-the-art solvers for CVRP or VRPTW. The goal of the experiment is to provide a relative comparison of a solver with and without the additional uncertainty-handling mechanisms revealing their price in performance. We also note that while separate scaling experiments were not conducted for the real-world pickup-delivery instances, the observed performance differences were very similar to what we reported on the benchmark instances.

Table 3. Average runtimes (in seconds) from the CVRP scaling experiment. B – baseline, I – inflation, D – deflation, P – penalties, C – chance constraints.

Instance	B	I	D	P	C
X-n101-k25	34.44	35.88	35.59	39.73	36.44
X-n125-k30	51.60	54.60	54.00	59.72	59.04
X-n153-k22	82.00	87.80	87.80	93.72	94.11
X-n176-k26	105.80	115.71	115.03	123.81	121.12
X-n200-k36	132.72	142.49	141.44	154.49	147.68
X-n223-k34	166.84	182.24	181.12	188.85	181.49
X-n251-k28	232.88	253.56	250.12	263.40	259.91
X-n275-k28	248.64	268.19	264.45	281.85	285.09
X-n303-k21	293.32	318.67	319.36	338.07	326.76
X-n327-k20	321.60	353.81	353.55	372.57	367.19
X-n351-k40	318.08	349.40	346.80	371.08	362.04
X-n376-k94	308.84	332.60	319.23	356.49	347.69
X-n401-k29	404.12	442.71	437.01	459.72	467.44
X-n420-k130	320.48	351.57	346.08	362.71	353.57
X-n449-k29	427.20	475.19	474.17	503.63	492.51
X-n469-k138	373.92	408.75	403.64	426.08	418.51
X-n502-k39	495.00	545.88	541.01	575.12	564.35
X-n613-k62	661.48	679.32	680.21	794.39	769.96
X-n701-k44	847.76	855.43	853.72	1,047.72	999.65
X-n801-k40	1,089.96	1,107.55	1,120.85	1,373.89	1,284.11
X-n916-k207	1,061.32	1,076.25	1,082.41	1,204.11	1,232.96
X-n1001-k43	1,571.76	1,608.24	1,589.04	1,961.63	1,845.00

Table 4. Average runtimes (in seconds) from the VRPTW scaling experiment. B – baseline, I – inflation, D – deflation, P^g – penalties (guided), P^u – penalties (unguided), C – chance constraints.

Instance	B	I	D	P ^g	P ^u	C
C101	33.92	28.75	26.32	165.11	35.28	157.48
C105	34.88	30.76	27.59	202.89	37.00	199.79
C109	37.88	34.99	31.56	865.07	42.61	851.19
C121	111.60	96.83	90.65	569.37	102.96	618.79
C125	113.40	106.73	97.79	683.33	114.43	719.13
C129	126.04	113.51	104.47	2,141.53	130.45	2,164.33
C131	197.24	181.47	160.12	1,067.45	180.11	1,131.76
C135	197.00	193.65	171.76	1,314.43	208.08	1,227.09
C139	208.64	200.47	184.55	2,580.40	225.01	2,426.39
C141	242.32	225.01	190.99	1,107.51	224.11	1,072.69
C145	232.12	222.85	207.77	1,364.05	244.59	1,251.71
C149	283.16	234.39	221.96	3,432.37	281.53	3,032.51
C151	308.68	278.80	246.79	1,480.79	312.11	1,474.20
C155	320.92	288.13	260.93	1,760.24	314.53	1,573.69
C159	340.28	301.49	268.24	2,916.09	356.83	2,596.69
C161	277.56	273.91	271.89	1,462.53	313.64	1,519.77
C181	403.24	400.75	387.80	2,002.12	436.91	2,053.97
C1101	542.24	542.12	539.20	2,429.59	576.48	2,306.33
R101	28.68	25.31	23.01	102.88	29.51	99.47
R105	30.60	26.61	24.20	146.76	32.40	139.53
R109	32.80	29.00	25.75	246.52	35.88	211.32
R121	110.04	96.35	90.87	538.04	108.64	552.36
R125	113.88	102.01	95.51	630.36	117.69	674.17
R129	115.80	101.85	95.11	864.48	121.60	898.77
R131	182.88	180.28	164.80	1,019.28	210.36	1,035.33
R135	184.88	180.03	168.15	1,199.16	217.19	1,163.53
R139	191.60	187.04	168.69	1,465.92	206.55	1,410.33
R141	229.16	216.20	195.35	1,169.16	230.63	1,132.00
R145	236.52	226.00	203.19	1,399.84	263.43	1,276.39
R149	231.12	222.57	203.68	1,611.24	264.36	1,560.19
R151	299.40	286.59	256.71	1,692.80	311.61	1,556.33
R155	301.36	280.44	261.16	1,678.87	300.75	1,656.39
R159	304.44	287.35	260.19	2,001.24	324.76	1,909.88
R161	279.60	276.81	283.20	1,590.68	341.29	1,665.36
R181	398.52	418.53	403.33	2,177.01	480.61	2,472.44
R1101	554.20	606.43	559.55	2,729.33	640.61	3,255.56
RC101	29.20	25.89	23.99	122.60	32.33	116.29
RC105	29.08	26.63	23.88	170.81	32.79	154.43
RC108	32.52	29.88	27.39	308.56	36.44	293.75
RC121	110.44	95.39	91.33	650.71	112.80	692.75
RC125	120.00	104.60	94.08	793.36	110.47	875.16
RC129	125.80	107.85	99.92	1,476.99	120.53	1,465.08
RC131	190.08	184.89	164.75	1,202.84	191.12	1,197.93
RC135	199.76	186.64	167.55	1,380.43	211.31	1,390.23
RC139	193.56	184.76	172.41	1,878.48	204.31	1,837.60
RC141	225.92	219.76	200.32	1,280.95	242.09	1,280.21
RC145	225.88	222.92	202.01	1,528.97	237.83	1,483.75
RC149	250.68	226.09	206.41	2,150.07	277.47	2,043.17
RC151	304.88	288.13	262.19	1,884.77	312.73	1,682.95
RC155	328.52	289.21	260.37	1,848.97	364.39	1,840.51
RC159	316.16	292.51	261.23	2,332.47	337.92	2,319.09
RC161	282.00	284.68	282.51	1,718.40	340.24	1,740.85
RC181	394.80	403.48	403.20	2,331.09	457.35	2,371.72
RC1101	557.88	559.04	560.61	2,946.27	638.13	2,712.67